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RAGDNet: A Region-Adjacency Graph for Semantic Segmentation of Mechanical Drawings Using Graph Convolutional Networks*

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Abstract. Mechanical engineering drawings, when represented as raster images, consist of thin strokes and standardized annotations laid out on a mostly empty background. Formulating segmentation purely on the pixel grid does not exploit this sparse, structured nature and forces models to process large amounts of irrelevant background. Reliable semantic segmentation is a key prerequisite for downstream applications such as retrieving similar drawings from large databases and automating cost estimation.

We present RAGDNet, an image-to-graph approach for semantic segmentation of mechanical drawings. Each drawing is converted into a Region Adjacency Graph (RAG), in which regions are nodes and edges that encode spatial relations between neighbouring regions. A Graph Neural Network (GNN) then predicts a semantic label for each region. We show that this graph construction, combined with a GNN, achieves competitive performance compared to CNN and ViT architectures, while using fewer trainable parameters and enabling fast inference on the region graph once it is available.

While this study focuses on mechanical drawings, the same graph construction principles could be explored for other technical line drawings exhibiting similarly sparse, structured content in raster form.

To evaluate our approach, we introduce a dataset generated from Computer-Aided Design (CAD) models derived from the ABC dataset, comprising 422 annotated drawings with pixel-level labels for four foreground classes: hidden lines, morphological contours, dimension symbols, and text. RAGDNet achieves a mean foreground mIoU of 0.833 on this dataset, compared to 0.826 for a U-Net baseline and 0.747 for SegFormer-B0 under the same evaluation setting. To promote reproducibility, we release the dataset together with the code.

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1 Introduction

Engineering drawings are a standard medium of technical communication across many industrial domains. They encode specifications that must be interpreted consistently by designers, manufacturers, inspectors, and suppliers. Although *engineering drawing* is a broad term that can include architectural plans, piping and instrumentation diagrams, electrical schematics, and assembly layouts, in this work we focus specifically on *mechanical drawings*: 2D drawings that describe a single manufactured component.

Such drawings generally convey two complementary types of information. On the one hand, *morphological* information, which defines the visible geometry of the part, i.e., its external shape and contours. On the other hand, annotation content, which supplements this geometry with functional intent: hidden lines, center lines, sectional views, dimensions, tolerances, surface finish requirements, material specifications, datum references, textual notes, etc. Figure 1 shows an example of this distinction, with the morphology in black and the annotations in color.

Fig. 1: Example of a mechanical drawing with different types of annotations.

Mechanical drawings are created with CAD tools, but they are often exchanged either as raster images or through vector exchange formats such as Drawing Exchange Format (DXF). In addition, many legacy drawings are only available as scanned raster images while the corresponding parts remain in use. Raster images carry no explicit semantics about drawing elements, and DXF files often provide only partial or tool-dependent semantics. Semantic segmentation therefore provides a practical means to recover element-level semantics.

This information can be leveraged for downstream applications, including retrieving similar drawings or parts from large databases [25]. It can also support automated cost estimation by enabling structured extraction of the drawing elements relevant to quoting and manufacturing [2].

Semantic segmentation assigns a semantic class to each pixel, and is widely used in domains such as autonomous driving and medical image analysis. In deep learning, progress on this task was initially driven by Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [19, 9, 8, 16], and has more recently been advanced by Vision Transformer (ViT) [10, 28]. However, most CNN and ViT architectures are designed for visually dense scenes, whereas mechanical drawings are dominated by empty space and convey information through thin strokes and sparse annotations. As a result, pixel-grid architectures spend a substantial fraction of their computation processing background rather than informative content.

To address this issue, we introduce RAGDNet, a methodology that converts mechanical drawings into a RAG to focus on relevant technical content while discarding the background. Our graph construction proceeds in four steps: (1) thinning of the binarized drawing to obtain a one-pixel-wide skeleton; (2) corner detection on the skeleton to split strokes at corners; (3) a marker-controlled watershed transform to expand skeleton branches into stroke regions; and (4) graph construction, where each region is encoded by its polygonal contour. We then connect nodes with directed edges using a k -nearest-neighbour rule based on spatial proximity. To learn on this graph, we use a GNN, introduced in Scarselli et al. [22], which operate on graph-structured data by iteratively aggregating information from neighbouring nodes. Finally, region predictions are projected back onto the pixel grid by assigning each pixel the label of its region.

Due to the scarcity of publicly available data in this domain, we accompany our method with a labeled dataset of 422 mechanical drawings in raster image format. This dataset enables a controlled evaluation of our approach and facilitates comparisons with standard pixel-based baselines such as CNN and ViT segmentation models.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces RAGDNet, describing how drawings are converted into a RAG and how the resulting graphs are processed by a graph neural network for region classification. Section 3 presents our publicly available dataset generated from CAD models, details the evaluation protocol, and reports quantitative and qualitative results, including comparisons to pixel-based baselines. Section 4 discusses related work. Finally, Section 5 summarizes findings and discusses limitations and future work.

2 Methodology

Semantic segmentation assigns a semantic class to each pixel, separating the heterogeneous elements of a drawing into meaningful categories. We address this task by reformulating segmentation as a region-based problem. Starting from a binarized drawing I , the method first constructs a directed graph, $G = (V, E) = \text{RAGD}_{[\tau_{\min}, \tau_{\max}], k}(I)$, then predicts one semantic label per region on G , and finally projects these region labels back onto the pixel grid.

The graph construction relies on two main parameters. The angular range $[\tau_{\min}, \tau_{\max}]$ controls the corner-based splitting, while k limits the number of neighbours retained per node in the graph. Both are treated as hyperparameters.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the successive stages used to build the region graph from the binary image, as detailed in Sections 2.1–2.4. The graph neural network used to perform region classification on the resulting graph is described in Section 2.5.

Fig. 2: Overview of RAGDNet graph construction pipeline.

2.1 Thinning of the binarised image

Our pipeline first extracts a clean one-pixel-wide skeleton that preserves junctions and stroke geometry. We binarize the input drawing into $I \in \{0, 1\}^{H \times W}$, where 1 denotes foreground strokes and 0 the background, and H and W denote the image height and width, respectively, and apply a thinning operator \mathcal{T} to obtain

$$\text{Skel} = \mathcal{T}(I), \quad \text{Skel} \in \{0, 1\}^{H \times W}.$$

We evaluated several classical thinning algorithms, including Zhang–Suen [31], MAT [27], Guo–Hall [14], and Lee [18]. While these methods share the same goal, they differ in their robustness to quantization noise and in how well they preserve sharp angles. In our experiments, Lee’s thinning produced the most stable junction structure and the most compact skeleton, with fewer spurious branches, and we adopt it as the default thinning operator in the remainder of this work.

2.2 Skeleton segmentation: junction and corner detection

Junction detection Junction detection is performed by counting the number of foreground neighbours of each skeleton pixel. Let $*$ denote 2D convolution, and define

$$K = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad D = \text{Skel} * K.$$

A pixel (i, j) is classified as a junction if $\text{Skel}_{ij} = 1$ and $D_{ij} \geq 3$, which follows from the standard property of one-pixel-wide skeletons: regular stroke points have two neighbours along the curve, whereas branching points have three or more. In Fig. 3, we show small examples of local patterns in Skel and how their degree values allow us to distinguish different topological features.

$\begin{matrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix}$	$\begin{matrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix}$	$\begin{matrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix}$	$\begin{matrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{matrix}$
(a) Endpoint, $D_{1,1} = 1$	(b) Internal seg- ment, $D_{1,1} = 2$	(c) T-junction, $D_{1,1} = 3$	(d) Cross-junction, $D_{1,1} = 4$

Fig. 3: Examples of skeleton pixel classification based on the degree matrix D .

Corner Detection Once junctions have been detected, the skeleton can be interpreted as a set of independent branches. Each branch is an ordered sequence of 8-connected skeleton pixels between two junctions or between a junction and an endpoint. Let $\Omega = \{1, \dots, H\} \times \{1, \dots, W\}$ denote the image domain and $B = (p_1, \dots, p_n)$ with $p_k = (x_k, y_k) \in \Omega$ a branch such that $\text{Skel}_{x_k, y_k} = 1$ for all k and $p_{k+1} \in \mathcal{N}_8(p_k)$, where \mathcal{N}_8 is the 8-neighbourhood.

Raw skeleton branches often contain small zigzags due to binarization and quantization noise. To obtain a cleaner geometric support for corner detection, we apply the Douglas–Peucker polyline simplification algorithm [12] to each branch with distance tolerance ε , yielding a simplified subsequence $\tilde{B} = \text{DP}(B, \varepsilon)$ with $|\tilde{B}| \leq |B|$. This reduces small oscillations while preserving the main shape and direction changes. In our experiments, we set $\varepsilon = 2.12$ pixels; this value is motivated by a simple geometric bound on quantization errors on the pixel grid, but we do not detail this derivation here.

Corners are then detected on the simplified branch \tilde{B} by measuring the local turning angle at each interior point. For three consecutive points $\tilde{p}_{i-1}, \tilde{p}_i, \tilde{p}_{i+1} \in \tilde{B}$, we define $\theta_i = \angle(\tilde{p}_{i-1}, \tilde{p}_i, \tilde{p}_{i+1})$ and classify \tilde{p}_i as a corner if $\tau_{\min} \leq \theta_i \leq \tau_{\max}$, where $(\tau_{\min}, \tau_{\max})$ are angular hyperparameters of our method. When this condition is satisfied, the branch is split at \tilde{p}_i into two shorter, geometrically consistent sub-branches.

2.3 Region expansion from skeleton branches

At the end of the corner-detection stage, the skeleton is decomposed into a set of disjoint branches. These branches do not cover the entire foreground of the drawing and must therefore be expanded to recover complete stroke regions. We use each branch as a marker from which a region grows to cover the corresponding stroke.

Region growth proceeds by progressively absorbing foreground pixels starting from these markers until the full foreground is covered. To control the expansion order, we define a pixel priority scheme: pixels located near the center of strokes are absorbed first, while pixels closer to stroke boundaries are absorbed later. This ordering yields stable regions anchored around the branch markers.

To define the pixel priority, we use the Chebyshev distance, which is consistent with 8-connectivity, and invert it so that pixels deeper from the background are processed first. In this priority map, smaller values correspond to higher priority. Figure 4 illustrates the resulting priority map.

This corresponds to a marker-controlled watershed algorithm [26]. The result of this process is shown in Fig. 6: each branch marker expands over the foreground until it meets neighbouring regions, producing a non-overlapping partition of the drawing.

Fig. 4: Inverted distance transform

Fig. 5: Watershed segmentation. Each color corresponds to one region.

2.4 Directed k -NN region graph

Starting from the non-overlapping stroke regions produced by the marker-controlled watershed, we construct a directed k -NN region graph $G = (V, E)$. The following paragraphs define the node set, node features, edge set, and edge features used to represent this graph. An overview is shown in Fig. 6.

NODES. Each region R_i is mapped to a node $v_i \in V$. For example, in Fig. 6, the watershed produces seven non-overlapping regions (seven distinct colors), hence the resulting graph has seven nodes, i.e., $|V| = 7$.

NODE FEATURES. For each region R_i , we extract its outer contour using a border-following algorithm [24] and simplify it with the Douglas–Peucker algorithm [12], yielding a polygon P_i . The node feature is the set of polygon vertices in absolute image coordinates.

EDGES. For each node v_i , we identify its k closest regions according to the polygon-to-polygon distance $d_{ij} := \min_{a \in P_i, b \in P_j} \|a - b\|_2$. For every neighbour v_j in this k -NN set, we add a directed edge $(v_j, v_i) \in E$, i.e., edges are oriented toward the reference node so that it receives messages from its k nearest neighbours. The resulting graph is sparse with at most $|E| \leq |V|k$ edges and is not necessarily symmetric.

EDGE FEATURES. Each directed edge (v_j, v_i) carries a geometric attribute vector $e_{ji} := [\hat{d}_{ij}, \hat{u}_{ij}^x, \hat{u}_{ij}^y]$, where \hat{d}_{ij} is d_{ij} normalized by the maximum edge distance in the graph, and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{ij} := (\hat{u}_{ij}^x, \hat{u}_{ij}^y)$ is the unit vector from the closest point on P_i to the closest point on P_j .³

³ Edge orientation is a modelling choice for message passing and should not be confused with $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{ij}$. The direction vector is defined by polygon geometry ($P_i \rightarrow P_j$) and is not tied to the chosen edge direction (v_j, v_i) .

Fig. 6: Directed k -NN region graph construction.

2.5 Graph neural network for region classification

We formulate semantic segmentation as node classification on the region graph $G = (V, E)$: each node is a region and edges connect k nearest neighbours. The network outputs one label per node. Below, we describe the architecture, training objective, and inference procedure.

ARCHITECTURE. Each region polygon P_i is encoded as a set of 2D points using a PointNet-style set encoder [7] with permutation-invariant mean and max pooling, producing a fixed-length node embedding.⁴ The embeddings are processed by a GATv2 network [5] followed by a node-wise Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) that outputs class logits. Figure 7 summarizes the architecture.

TRAINING. We train with node-level cross-entropy, using region labels obtained by majority vote over the pixels in each region.

INFERENCE. Predicted region labels are projected back onto the pixel grid by assigning each foreground pixel the label of its region.

Fig. 7: RAGDNet deep learning architecture for region classification.

3 Experiments

This section describes the dataset we built and the experiments conducted to evaluate our approach. The generated dataset and the code required to reproduce all experiments, including training scripts, are available at <https://github.com/Alewep/RAGDnet>.

⁴ An embedding is a fixed-length vector representation learned from an object, here a region.

3.1 Dataset

We build a synthetic dataset of mechanical drawings derived from the ABC dataset, which contains CAD models. For each CAD model, we automatically generate one or more engineering drawings using Autodesk Fusion [3] and export them as DXF files. Using a controlled generation process is important here because it produces DXF files with consistent structure and metadata conventions across drawings, which makes entity parsing reliable and reproducible. We exploit this metadata to generate pixel-level ground-truth labels. We implement a dedicated parsing and rasterization pipeline based on the `ezdxf` library [20] to map DXF entities to four semantic foreground classes: morphology, hidden, dimension, and text.

The resulting dataset contains 422 labeled drawings with pixel-level ground truth, exported as color images for visualization. All labels are produced automatically from the CAD outputs, without manual correction or curation. Qualitative examples are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Examples of mechanical drawings from the dataset.

3.2 Experimental setup

We evaluate all methods using 5-fold cross-validation on the dataset described in Section 3.1. The 422 drawings are partitioned into five splits; for each fold, four splits (80%) are used for training and one split (20%) for validation. We report the average performance over the five folds. Performance is measured using the mean Intersection-over-Union (mIoU) over the four foreground classes. For a given class, the IoU is the ratio between the number of pixels correctly predicted as belonging to that class and the total number of pixels that are predicted or labeled as that class. The mIoU is the average IoU across the four classes. We compare two RAGDNet variants and pixel-based baselines:

- RAGDNet-GAT (ours): Same architecture as shown in Fig. 7.
- RAGDNet-MLP: Node-wise MLP baseline followed by a linear classifier. It uses the same region encoder as Fig. 7 and keeps the architecture unchanged, except that the GATv2 convolution layers are replaced by an MLP with hidden widths [512, 1024, 256, 128]. The RAGDNet-MLP has 941K trainable parameters, comparable to the 881K of RAGDNet-GAT.
- U-Net: Five-level encoder–decoder with skip connections and base width 64, ending with a 1×1 convolution for per-pixel logits [21].
- SegFormer-B0: Transformer-based baseline using SegFormer [28]. We instantiate the B0 architecture from a public configuration, adapt the segmentation head to our classes, and train from scratch without external pretraining.

Training protocols differ in the input representation. Graph-based models are trained on complete graphs, one per drawing; mini-batches contain several graphs with varying numbers of nodes. Pixel-based baselines are trained with data augmentation using random 512×512 crops and horizontal flips. All models are trained with cross-entropy loss. For graph-based models, cross-entropy is computed at the node level using region labels derived from pixel annotations; for pixel-based models, it is computed at the pixel level. We set the graph-construction parameters to $\tau_{\min} = 75$, $\tau_{\max} = 115$, and $k = 2$, as this configuration gave the best performance among the tested angle ranges $[\tau_{\min}, \tau_{\max}] \in [75, 115], [60, 130], [45, 145]$ and neighbourhood sizes $k \in 1, 2, 3$.

At evaluation time, all methods operate on full-resolution drawings at their native size: pixel-based baselines run inference directly on the full image, while graph-based models run on the complete region graph extracted from the same drawing.

3.3 Results

Cross-validation results are summarized in Table 1, reporting per-class IoU and mean IoU (mIoU) over the four foreground classes. RAGDNet-GAT reaches the best overall mIoU and performs particularly well on *hidden lines*. This class is sparse and visually ambiguous, and is often confused with other thin strokes. The gain over both pixel-based baselines suggests that message passing on the region graph helps disambiguate such elements by leveraging local relational context. This is supported by the comparison with RAGDNet-MLP, which keeps the same region encoder but replaces the GATv2 convolution layers with an MLP and drops substantially on hidden lines.

Pixel-based baselines show a different profile. U-Net achieves the best IoU on *morphology* and *dimension*, which likely benefits from dense multi-scale feature extraction and skip connections. SegFormer-B0 is competitive on the dominant classes but exhibits higher variance across folds, especially on *hidden lines*. Overall, region-graph message passing and dense pixel-grid processing appear complementary: pixel-based models rely on local visual evidence, whereas the proposed graph-based model is more effective for sparse and visually ambiguous annotations.

Table 1: Cross-validation performance in terms of per-class IoU and mean IoU (mIoU) over the four foreground classes.

Method	Morphology	Dimension	Hidden Lines	Text	mIoU
RAGDNet-GAT (ours)	0.88 ±0.01	0.84 ±0.02	0.68 ±0.05	0.94 ±0.01	0.833 ±0.011
RAGDNet-MLP	0.87 ±0.01	0.78 ±0.03	0.51 ±0.04	0.88 ±0.01	0.761 ±0.007
U-Net	0.94 ±0.02	0.88 ±0.03	0.56 ±0.04	0.93 ±0.04	0.826 ±0.030
SegFormer-B0	0.92 ±0.02	0.83 ±0.03	0.32 ±0.15	0.92 ±0.04	0.747 ±0.060

Figure 9 shows qualitative segmentation examples produced by RAGDNet-GAT on representative mechanical drawings. For consistency, we report visualizations from the first cross-validation fold only and use samples from the corresponding validation set. Predictions are shown for all foreground classes, including morphology, dimensions, hidden lines, and text.

Fig. 9: Examples of qualitative results.

3.4 Model size and inference speed

To complement accuracy metrics, we report the number of trainable parameters and CPU wall-clock runtime on an Intel Core i7 vPro processor, averaged over 422 drawings, in Table 2. Pixel-based baselines are timed using full-resolution inference. For RAGDNet, we decompose the end-to-end time into graph construction (*Pre*) and the GNN forward pass (*Inf*), with $Total = Pre + Inf$. Graph construction can be performed offline and cached, so repeated processing of the same drawing reduces to the *Inf* cost.

Table 2: Model size and CPU timing on an Intel Core i7 vPro over 422 drawings.

Method	Params	Pre (s)	Inf (s)	Total (s)
RAGDNet-GAT	0.881M	11.8355±10.7661	0.0352±0.0334	11.8707±10.7662
U-Net	31.0M	–	12.2634±5.2335	12.2634±5.2335
SegFormer-B0	3.75M	–	7.4089±6.4422	7.4089±6.4422

These results indicate that the learned part of RAGDNet is lightweight: once the region graph is available, inference takes 0.035 s on average with a 0.881M-parameter model. In the current prototype, the end-to-end runtime is dominated by graph construction, implemented in Python. One way to amortize this cost is to cache the region graph, i.e., store the precomputed graph for each drawing so that it does not need to be rebuilt across runs. This is useful during training, where the same drawings are revisited across many epochs, and in corpus-scale settings such as document or CAD databases, where graphs can be built once offline and segmentation can then be run on demand with low latency. In both cases, re-running inference after a model update does not require rebuilding graphs, reducing per-run cost to the *Inf* time.

4 Related Works

4.1 Graph neural networks for inductive node classification

Early GNNs such as GCN showed that simple convolutions on a normalised adjacency matrix achieve strong results on citation benchmarks, but in a transductive setting where a single fixed graph is used for both training and testing [17]. To handle inductive scenarios with unseen graphs, GraphSAGE introduced neighbourhood aggregation functions and established Reddit and PPI as standard inductive benchmarks [15]. Subsequent models such as GAT and GATv2 replace simple aggregation with attention mechanisms, further improving inductive node classification.

4.2 Graph based image analysis using Graph neural networks

Recent work has also combined region graphs with graph neural networks by using superpixels as graph nodes and learning over their spatial connectivity. Superpixels are often obtained with SLIC [1]. Several recent approaches then process the resulting superpixel graphs with GNNs, including graph attention networks [4] and graph convolutional networks [11, 23]. However, SLIC typically relies on appearance cues such as colour and texture to define regions and edges, which are poorly suited to binary line drawings. In contrast, we build a region graph tailored to mechanical drawings and learn on it with a graph neural network.

4.3 GNN-based segmentation of sketches and technical drawings

A common strategy for sketch and drawing segmentation is to convert the drawing into a graph and apply a GNN for node classification. SketchGNN [30] follows this approach for freehand sketches by using stroke points as graph nodes. For floor plans, FloorPlanCAD, PanCADNet and follow-up methods combine convolutional features with GNNs on vector graphics [13], including attention-based variants such as GAT-CADNet and VectorGraphNET [33, 6], which achieve competitive semantic performance, close to the point-based CADSpotting method [29]. All these methods assume vector input, with nodes representing geometric primitives from the vector file, and are therefore not directly applicable to raster-only data. Closer to our setting, prior work applies graph-based learning to engineering drawings by constructing graphs from extracted drawing components [32]. Our approach differs by (i) using a corner-splitting strategy that is less sensitive to quantization noise, (ii) operating in the raster domain with region-based nodes, (iii) learning node features end-to-end, and (iv) increasing graph connectivity with a directed k -NN rule.

5 Discussion & Future Work

We study semantic segmentation of mechanical drawings, documents characterized by thin, structured strokes and large empty backgrounds. To better match this structure, we introduce two contributions. First, we release a dataset of mechanical drawings with pixel-level labels for four foreground classes. Second, we propose RAGDNet, a region-graph approach that converts each drawing into a region adjacency graph and applies a graph neural network to predict one semantic label per region before projecting predictions back to the pixel grid. Experiments show that region-graph representations form a strong basis for this task, yielding competitive accuracy with compact models and low inference cost once the region graph is available.

Our study has two main limitations. First, the dataset currently covers a limited set of semantic classes and drawing conventions, which does not reflect the full diversity of industrial practice. Second, RAGDNet relies on a multi-stage image-to-graph construction pipeline, so errors or biases introduced in early steps can propagate to the final region graph and affect segmentation.

We plan to broaden coverage by applying our pipeline to an industrial dataset provided by a partner; this requires re-annotation to match our label definitions and to extend the taxonomy beyond the four foreground classes. To reduce sensitivity to preprocessing, we will move toward a less heuristic and more learnable image-to-graph pipeline, and investigate differentiable formulations that facilitate end-to-end training. Validation on the partner dataset will assess performance under industrial conditions. Finally, a longer-term goal is to extend the approach beyond semantic segmentation toward panoptic segmentation of mechanical drawings, enabling instance-level separation of individual annotations within each class.

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